

Microscopic Examination of Parasite Contamination and Application of HACCP in Food Safety: A Comparative Study of Manila and Osaka

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Abstract

Food safety is a global public health concern, particularly in relation to parasitic contamination of food, which poses significant risks to consumers. This study presents a comparative analysis of food safety practices and parasite contamination in food establishments in Manila, Philippines, and Osaka, Japan. Using a descriptive-comparative design, the study integrates structured observations, microscopic examination of food and water samples, and environmental assessments. Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) summarize hygiene practices and contamination observations, while qualitative analysis compares regulatory compliance and food handling behaviors across contexts. Results indicate generally high compliance with hygiene standards in both cities, with no parasites detected in most sampled foods, though isolated contamination risks were observed. The findings highlight the role of regulatory enforcement, environmental management, and food establishment practices in maintaining food safety and inform evidence-based recommendations for improving food safety systems, particularly in developing urban settings.

Keywords: comparative study, food safety, HACCP, microscopic examination, parasite contamination, public health, food establishment hygiene, water quality

Research Question

How do food safety practices and observed parasite contamination in food establishments in Manila, Philippines, compare to those in Osaka, Japan, based on microscopic examination and structured observation?

Objectives

This study aims to:

1. Compare food safety practices in food establishments in Manila, Philippines, and Osaka, Japan, using structured observation of hygiene standards, food handling procedures, and sanitation measures.
2. Identify the presence or absence of parasite contamination in food and water samples through microscopic examination.
3. Examine environmental factors such as cleanliness, food storage, and handling conditions in relation to observed contamination risks.
4. Analyze how regulatory frameworks and cultural practices influence food safety compliance in both cities.

Introduction

Food safety is a global concern due to its essential role in ensuring food security and public health (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations [FAO], 2019). Contaminated food hampers socioeconomic development, overloads healthcare systems, and compromises economic growth and trade (FAO, 2019). From a medical perspective, food contamination can cause diseases such as botulism, viral gastroenteritis, and hepatitis A (Occupational Safety and Health Administration [OSHA], n.d.). The World Health Organization (WHO, 2024) estimates approximately 600 million cases of foodborne illness and 420,000 deaths annually. While most foodborne diseases are caused by bacteria such as *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and enterohaemorrhagic *Escherichia coli*, parasites (e.g., tapeworms and roundworms), viruses (e.g., norovirus), chemical toxins, and prions also contribute significantly to disease burden.

Food contamination can occur at any stage of the food production chain—from farm to table—including production, processing, transportation, storage, and preparation (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], n.d.). In developing countries such as the Philippines, foodborne disease outbreaks are more prevalent due to poverty, inadequate sanitation, and limited regulatory enforcement (Azanza et al., 2019). Between 2005 and 2018, most foodborne disease outbreaks in the Philippines were associated with foods prepared in institutional settings

such as canteens, restaurants, and catering services, as well as in households (Azanza et al., 2019). More recent studies have reported the presence of parasites in Manila street foods, including *Ascaris* spp. and *Entamoeba* spp. (Escutin et al., 2024).

In contrast, Japan reports at least 1,000 confirmed cases of food poisoning annually, though a declining trend has been observed over the past decade (Watari et al., 2020; Kumagai et al., 2020). While bacteria and viruses remain the primary causes, parasites and toxins also contribute to foodborne illness, particularly among tourists (Watari et al., 2020). Japan's Food Sanitation Act (Act No. 233 of 1947) establishes comprehensive standards for food safety, requiring all food-related businesses to implement sanitation management systems based on Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) principles since 2021.

Both Japan and the Philippines have enacted national food safety laws—Japan's Food Sanitation Act (1947) and the Philippines' Food Safety Act (Republic Act No. 10611 of 2013)—which outline regulations on food handling, sanitation, labeling, and business operation. However, while Japan mandates HACCP-based hygiene management for all food operators, HACCP implementation in the Philippines remains largely voluntary and is primarily adopted by large-scale and export-oriented enterprises (DA Press Office, 2021). Micro and small food businesses in the Philippines face challenges such as limited financial resources, insufficient training, and technical constraints, resulting in inconsistent compliance (Karen, 2016).

Given these differences in regulatory enforcement, infrastructure, and cultural practices, this study seeks to compare food safety practices and parasite contamination in Manila and Osaka. By integrating microscopic examination with observational and environmental assessments, this research aims to contribute empirical evidence to inform food safety policy, food establishment training, and public health interventions in both contexts.

Research Design

This study employs a **descriptive-comparative mixed-methods design**, integrating qualitative and quantitative data collected concurrently to provide a comprehensive analysis of food safety practices and parasite contamination.

Microscopic examination of food and water samples from food establishments in Manila and Osaka serves as the primary quantitative method for detecting parasite presence. Qualitative data are obtained through structured observations assessing hygiene practices, food handling procedures, and environmental conditions such as cleanliness, storage, and waste management.

By triangulating observational data, microscopic findings, and environmental assessments, the study aims to identify patterns, contextual influences, and comparative differences in food safety practices and contamination risk across the two urban settings.

Participants or Subjects

Participants include food handlers and employees directly involved in food preparation, handling, and service in food establishments in Manila, Philippines, and Osaka, Japan. These individuals play a critical role in maintaining food safety, as their practices directly influence hygiene, contamination risk, and consumer protection. Participants are drawn from a diverse range of establishments, including restaurants, cafeterias, convenience stores, and street food establishments, to ensure representation across business types. Only personnel actively engaged in food handling and preparation are included to ensure relevance to the research objectives.

Data Collection Methods

1. Observation of Food Establishments

- *Direct Observation:* Food establishments in both cities were observed for food handling practices, cleanliness, and environmental conditions (e.g., proximity to waste, food storage, and use of protective equipment).
- *Checklists:* A structured checklist documented hygiene practices, including handwashing, utensil sanitation, use of gloves, face masks, hair nets, and adherence to food safety guidelines.

2. Sampling

- *Food and Water Samples:* Samples were collected from food establishments, focusing on cooked foods and ready-to-eat meals.
- *Sampling Locations:* Samples were obtained from both high-traffic (e.g., markets, malls) and low-traffic areas to assess variation in contamination risk.

3. Microscopic Analysis

- Food and water samples were examined under a microscope to detect parasite eggs, cysts, or larvae. Observations focused on presence or absence rather than species-level identification.

4. **Water Quality Assessment**

- Water samples were tested for temperature, pH, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), and dissolved oxygen, with results compared to national drinking water standards.

Materials and Equipment

- Microscope (including pocket microscope for field use)
 - Sterile sample containers and swabs
 - Structured observation checklist
 - Camera for documentation
 - Water quality probes (pH meter, TDS meter)
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Data Analysis Methods

Quantitative Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

- Frequency and percentage distributions for parasite presence or absence.
- Summary counts of hygiene practices and environmental conditions.

No inferential statistical tests were applied due to limited sample size and absence of sufficient variation in contamination outcomes.

Qualitative Analysis

Observational data were categorized based on adherence to food safety norms, including hygiene practices, food handling procedures, and environmental sanitation. A comparative thematic

analysis was conducted to identify similarities and differences between food safety practices in Manila and Osaka, with attention to cultural, procedural, and regulatory influences.

Ethical Considerations

The study adheres to ethical research standards by:

- Respecting the culture, customs, and practices of local communities in both Manila and Osaka.
 - Ensuring non-intrusive observation and avoiding any interference with business operations.
 - Maintaining environmental cleanliness during fieldwork (CLAYGO principle).
 - Preserving the anonymity of establishments and participants by omitting identifying information.
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Limitations of the Methodology

Sampling Size: The limited number of establishments restricts generalizability and prevents inferential statistical analysis. Some samples from the Philippines and Osaka were not directly comparable.

Procedures

1. Preparation

- 1.1 Compile and review food safety laws, regulations, and policies in the Philippines and Japan.
- 1.2 Identify a diverse sample of food establishments in Manila and Osaka.
- 1.3 Develop structured observation checklists for hygiene, food handling, and environmental factors.

2. Water Quality Assessment

2.1 pH Level

- Calibrate the pH meter using standard buffer solutions.
- Collect a water sample, insert the probe, allow the reading to stabilize, and record the result.

2.2 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

- Calibrate the TDS meter.
- Insert the probe into the water sample, allow the reading to stabilize, record the value, and rinse the electrodes.

2.3 Water Safety Testing

- Use water test strips according to manufacturer instructions.
- Compare color changes to the reference chart and record findings.

3. Food Sampling and Microscopic Examination

3.1 Sample Collection

- Collect food samples using sterile swabs and containers, ensuring samples represent food served directly to customers.

3.2 Slide Preparation

- Place the specimen on a slide, add a mounting medium, carefully apply a coverslip, and remove excess fluid.

3.3 Microscopic Examination

- Use a pocket microscope and external light sources to observe samples.
- Record the presence or absence of parasite eggs, cysts, or larvae.

3.4 Data Recording and Analysis

- Document all microscopic findings.
- Compare results between Manila and Osaka to identify patterns and differences.

4. Hygiene Observation

- Observe food establishment practices during food preparation and service.
- Record hygiene behaviors, food storage conditions, waste management, and environmental cleanliness using the checklist.

Justification for Method Choices

Legal and Health Standards

Reviewing food safety laws in both countries ensures alignment with public health standards and highlights the importance of regulatory compliance in preventing foodborne illness (World Health Organization, n.d.).

Water Quality Testing

Monitoring pH and TDS ensures water safety, as contaminated water can promote microbial growth and contribute to food contamination (Ding & Feng, 2022).

Microbial and Parasitic Analysis

Microscopic examination enables early detection of contamination, reducing the risk of foodborne outbreaks and protecting public health (Elexbio, n.d.).

Hygiene and Sanitation Observation

Qualitative observation provides insight into real-world compliance with food safety protocols and identifies areas for improvement and intervention (Institute of Food Science & Technology, n.d.).

Research Locale

Metro Manila, Philippines

Metro Manila is characterized by a vibrant street food culture, offering affordable and accessible food but posing challenges to food safety compliance. Despite consumer awareness of food safety regulations, adherence remains inconsistent (Labana et al., 2024). This study examines food establishment knowledge, attitudes, and practices in this context.

Osaka, Japan

Osaka, known as the “Kitchen of Japan,” maintains strict food safety standards under the Food Sanitation Act (1947). Its diverse food establishments provide an ideal setting to examine the effectiveness of regulatory enforcement and cultural norms in ensuring food safety.

Significance of the Study

This study contributes to:

- **Public Health Awareness:** Identifying how food establishment practices influence contamination risk.
- **Comparative Insight:** Highlighting differences and similarities in food safety systems between Manila and Osaka.
- **Policy Development:** Informing evidence-based food safety policies and interventions.
- **Educational Value:** Providing data to support training programs for food handlers.
- **Cross-Cultural Understanding:** Promoting the exchange of best practices across cultural context.

Results (Qualitative Observations)

A total of 10 food samples were examined (5 from Osaka and 5 from Manila). Parasites were not detected in 9 samples (90%). One sample from Manila showed the presence of a fruit fly larva.

Table 1. Microscopic Examination of Food Samples from Japan

Category	Food	Microscopic Findings
Convenience Store	Onigiri	No parasites observed
Cafeteria	Fried rice	No parasites observed
Fresh Food	Sashimi	No parasites observed
Street Food	Takoyaki	No parasites observed
Restaurant	Ramen	No parasites observed

Japan

- Onigiri samples were obtained from clean convenience store environments where food was individually packed; glove use was inconsistent, but no parasites were observed. Takoyaki stalls were clean but open-air, with partial glove use and no parasite presence

detected. Sashimi was prepared in clean open seating areas without personal protective equipment; no parasites were observed. Milk ice cream establishments were air-conditioned with separate preparation areas and demonstrated high sanitation standards. Cafeteria spaghetti and pork dishes showed full PPE compliance and no parasite contamination.

- Pufferfish sashimi was not microscopically examined due to regulatory safety constraints; no adverse health incidents were reported

Table 2. Microscopic Examination of Food Samples from the Philippines

Category	Food	Microscopic Findings
Convenience Store	Onigiri	No parasites observed
Restaurant	Tonkotsu Ramen	No parasites observed
Cafeteria	Spaghetti	No parasites observed; one instance of fruit fly larva noted
Beverage/Water	Soup	No parasites observed
Beverage/Water	Tap Water	No parasites observed

Philippines

- Tonkotsu ramen samples were obtained from clean environments with full PPE compliance; no parasites were observed. Onigiri from convenience stores showed clean handling practices without glove use and no parasite presence. Cafeteria spaghetti samples were generally clean, though one instance of a fruit fly larva was observed. Soup and tap water samples were examined, with no parasites detected.
 - Overall, most samples from both cities showed no parasite contamination, though isolated contamination risks were observed in select Philippine samples.
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Discussion

The findings indicate generally high compliance with hygiene standards in both Manila and Osaka establishments sampled, with no parasites detected in most food samples. However, isolated observations—such as the presence of a fruit fly larva in a Philippine cafeteria sample—highlight the potential for contamination even in regulated environments.

Japan’s legally mandated HACCP framework and rigorous enforcement mechanisms likely contribute to the consistent hygiene practices observed. Food handlers in Japanese establishments demonstrated higher compliance with personal protective equipment use, separation of preparation and service areas, and environmental control measures. In contrast, while many Philippine establishments exhibited good hygiene practices, inconsistencies were observed, particularly in glove use and the simultaneous handling of money and food.

The absence of parasites in most samples does not contradict existing literature documenting parasite contamination in street foods, especially in developing urban contexts. Rather, it suggests that selected establishments may represent higher compliance environments, emphasizing the importance of broader monitoring and enforcement.

Environmental conditions, including cleanliness, waste management, and water quality, were generally within acceptable standards in both cities. However, more consistent inspection and monitoring are recommended, particularly in Manila, where informal food sectors remain prevalent.

Conclusion

This comparative study highlights the importance of regulatory enforcement, hygiene practices, and environmental management in reducing contamination risks in food establishments. While both Manila and Osaka demonstrated generally acceptable food safety practices in the sampled

establishments, Japan's mandatory HACCP framework and consistent enforcement contributed to more uniform compliance.

The Philippines, despite having comprehensive food safety legislation, faces challenges in implementation, particularly among small and informal food businesses. By integrating microscopic examination with structured observation and environmental assessment, this study provides descriptive evidence to inform food safety policy, food establishment training, and public health interventions.

Strengthening HACCP adoption, enhancing food handler education, and improving regulatory enforcement can significantly reduce the risk of foodborne illness and improve consumer protection in developing urban food systems.

Recommendations

To strengthen food safety systems and address observed gaps, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Expand HACCP Implementation:** Extend mandatory HACCP adoption to micro and small food enterprises, supported by government-funded training and technical assistance.
2. **Enhance Food Handler Training:** Implement regular, standardized training programs through local government units, particularly for street food establishment.
3. **Improve Physical Infrastructure:** Upgrade food vending environments to ensure proper waste disposal, ventilation, and separation of preparation and service areas.
4. **Strengthen Water Quality Monitoring:** Integrate routine water testing into food safety inspections to prevent waterborne contamination.
5. **Increase Regulatory Enforcement:** Enhance inspection frequency and enforcement mechanisms under existing food safety laws.
6. **Promote Public Awareness:** Educate consumers on food safety practices to encourage informed choices and accountability among food establishments.

Declarations

Author Contributions

All student authors contributed to data collection, observation, analysis, and manuscript preparation. The adviser supervised the research design, guided analysis, and reviewed and edited the manuscript for publication.

Data Availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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